

Prospective Assessment of the Clinical and Radiological Parameters for Predicting the Difficult Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy

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Abstract

Aim: The aim of this study to Predicting difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy

Material and methods: The prospective study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College Kishanganj, Bihar, India from May 2019 to April 2020.

Results: In present study patients above 18 years only were included. Majority of patients in the study were in the age group of 30-40 years (30 out of 50). There were 40 females and 10 males. Only symptom duration of >1yr, history of hospitalization for acute cholecystitis and BMI >30 were statistically significant predictor of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy (Table 1). Analysis of risk factors as a group showed that only clinical risk factors achieved significant predictive value (p value 0.005). Radiological risk factors i.e., small, contracted gall bladder, gall bladder wall thickness >3mm and single large stone did not show significant effect either individually (p values - 0.955, 0.132, 0.088 respectively) or as a group (p value - 0.066). The only biochemical adverse factor taken into consideration, deranged LFT also did not show significant association with difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy (p value - 0.182).

Conclusion: Good clinical assessment is the most significant predictor of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Radiological predictors have inconsistent predictive value due to dependence on various factors beyond surgeon. So, it is important for surgeons working with infrastructural constraints to apply good clinical judgment and arrange specialized instruments, expertise, convert if necessary or refer to a specialized centre and counsel patients accordingly.

Keywords: laparoscopic cholecystectomy, predictors, difficulties

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Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (LC) is the gold standard treatment for symptomatic cholelithiasis.

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy provides a safe and effective treatment for most patients with symptomatic gallstones [1]

and is the treatment of choice for cholelithiasis. It has now become the most common operation performed by general surgeons [2]. Since the introduction of laparoscopic cholecystectomy, the number of cholecystectomy performed worldwide

increasing every year [3]. The advantages of laparoscopic cholecystectomy are earlier return to bowel function, less postoperative pain, cosmetics, shorter length of hospital stay, earlier return to full activity, and decreased overall cost [4,6]. However, of all Laparoscopic cholecystectomies, 1-13% requires conversion to an open for various reasons. Thus, for surgeons it would be helpful to establish criteria that would predict difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy and conversion preoperatively. But there is no clear consensus among the laparoscopic surgeons regarding the parameters predicting the difficult dissection and conversion to open cholecystectomy.

Material and Methods

The prospective study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery, MGM Medical College Kishanganj, Bihar, India from May 2019 to April 2020.

Methodology

50 Patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy for symptomatic gall stones in a single unit were included. Patients with current acute cholecystitis, CBD stone, concomitant another procedure and those not willing to be part of study were excluded. Study protocol was approved by institutional committee. Preoperative risk factors assessed were clinical (age, gender, duration of symptoms, BMI, H/O attack of acute cholecystitis, past history of abdominal surgery), radiological (on USG gall bladder wall thickness >3mm, single large stone in Hartmann's pouch, small, contracted gall bladder) and biochemical (deranged LFT). Time was calculated from veress needle insertion till port closure. Overall time >60 min was also considered as difficult

laparoscopic cholecystectomy. All surgeries were done under GA by standard four port technique. CO₂ pneumoperitoneum at 12mm Hg was used.

Statistics Analysis

Data recording was done in predesigned proforma. All the data was entered in Microsoft Excel. For analysis purpose all predictors were stratified into two groups i.e. age <50yrs and >50yrs, Symptoms duration <1yr and >1 year, BMI <30 and 30 or above. Chi square test was used to derive p value of difference between two strata of predictors. P value of <0.05 was taken as significant. Correlation coefficient along with p value was calculated to find relationship between risk factor and type of intraoperative difficulty.

Results

In present study patients above 18 years only were included. Majority of patients in the study were in the age group of 30-40 years (30 out of 50). There were 40 females and 10 males. Only symptom duration of >1yr, history of hospitalization for acute cholecystitis and BMI >30 were statistically significant predictor of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy (Table 1). Analysis of risk factors as a group showed that only clinical risk factors achieved significant predictive value (p value 0.005). Radiological risk factors i.e., small, contracted gall bladder, gall bladder wall thickness >3mm and single large stone did not show significant effect either individually (p values - 0.955, 0.132, 0.088 respectively) or as a group (p value - 0.066). The only biochemical adverse factor taken into consideration, deranged LFT also did not show significant association with difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy (p value - 0.182).

Table 1: Predictive association between risk factors and intraoperative outcome

Risk factor		Level	Intraoperative outcome		P value
			Easy (%)	Difficult (%)	
Clinical	Age	>50 yrs	4 (40)	6(60)	0.0217
		<50 yrs	26(65)	14(35)	
	Gender	Male	5 (50)	5 (50)	0.572
		Female	25(62.5)	15(37.5)	
	symptoms duration	>1 yr	0	7(100)	0.013*
		<1 yr	30(69.7)	13(30.2)	
	Past abdominal surgery	Yes	1 (50)	1(50)	0.955
		No	29 (60.4)	19 (39.5)	
	H/O acute cholecystitis	Yes	0	8(100)	0.004*
		No	30(61.2)	19(38.7)	
BMI	>30	2 (66.6)	1(33.3)	0.049*	
	<30	28 (59.5)	19 (40.4)		
Radiological	GB small wall	>3mm	1(20)	4 (80)	0.132
		<3mm	29 (64.4)	16 (35.6)	
	Small cintr. GB	Yes	1(50)	1(50)	0.955
		No	29(60.4)	19(39.5)	
	Single large stone	Yes	4 (20)	1(80)	0.088
		No	26 (57.7)	19 (42.2)	
Biochemical	Deranged LFT	Yes	2 (33.3)	4 (66.6)	0.182
		No	28 (63.6)	16(36.3)	
	Clinical adverse factor (combined)	Yes	7 (30.4)	16 (69.5)	0.006*
		No	23 (85.1)	4(14.81)	
	Radiological adverse factor	Yes	1 (10)	7(90)	0.066
		No	29(69.04)	13(30.9)	

Table 2: Correlation between risk factor and type of intraoperative difficulty

		Diff access	Idenof GB	Grasping of GB	Adhesiolysis	Calot dissectn	Duct clipn	Diff. in GB dissectn	Difficulty in extract GB	Bile spill
H/O Past surgery	Correlation coefficient	-0.06	-0.06	0.05	0.10	-0.16	-0.06	0.1	-0.07	-0.09
	p value	0.73	0.73	0.78	0.54	0.29	0.64	0.30	0.69	0.58
H/O Ac.	Corelatn coeffi.	-0.12	0.13	.424	0.549	0.356	0.23	0.328	0.08	0.15
chole.	p value	0.46	0.42	0.003	<0.002	0.013	0.129	0.021	0.63	0.35
LFT	Corelatn coeffi.	0.15	-.11	0.03	-0.02	-.07	0.07	-0.07	.307	0.18
	p value	0.34	0.49	0.88	0.94	0.68	0.70	0.70	0.032	0.25
GB Wall thickness	Corelatn coeffi.	0.21	-.09	0.28	-0.08	-.12	-0.12	0	.394	0.07
	p value	0.18	0.57	0.06	0.62	0.45	0.45	1	0.006	0.70
Small/contracted GB	Corelatn coeffi.	-0.06	-0.06	0.05	0.10	0.07	0.28	-0.11	-0.06	0.22
	p value	0.73	0.73	0.78	0.54	0.69	0.07	0.49	0.69	0.15
Large/single stone in GB neck	Corelatn coeffi.	0.13	0.13	0.18	0.09	0.04	0.17	-0.04	0.15	0.05
	p value	0.42	0.42	0.25	0.59	0.87	0.29	0.87	0.35	0.80
BMI	Corelatn coeffi.	-.378	-.12	0.10	0.07	0.07	0.09	0.20	.359	0.343
	p value	0.008	0.48	0.52	0.70	0.69	0.61	0.19	0.012	0.016

Correlation coefficient significance >0.3 weak, >0.5 moderate, >0.7 strong, P value <0.05 Significant, # nonsignificant values i.e., correlation coefficient <0.3 and p value >0.05 shown

only up to two places after decimal. Correlation coefficient and p value of correlation between risk factor and type of difficulty encountered intraoperatively is shown in table 2. History of acute cholecystitis was associated with difficult calot's triangle dissection, adhesiolysis, difficult gall bladder dissection from liver bed as well as difficulty in grasping of Hartmann's pouch. BMI >30 was associated with difficult peritoneal access as well as extraction of gall bladder from thick abdominal wall.

Discussion

Some studies have reported old age as a significant risk factor for difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy [7,8]. Most of these studies have taken 50 yrs as cut off for this purpose. But in present study age had no significant effect on intraoperative difficulty (p value - 0.216). This finding is consistent with Gupta N and Acharya A [9,10]. 80% (40/50) of patients in present study were females. Higher incidence of gallstone in females has been suggested due to the effect of estrogen and progesterone on biliary cholesterol level and gallbladder motility [11,12].

Relationship between male sex and difficult cholecystectomy is controversial. Some literature suggests that male gender is a risk factor for difficult cholecystectomy [13,14]. Since cholelithiasis is considered to be predominantly disease of females, males may be diagnosed late. It may result in significant adhesions due to repeated attacks of inflammation before diagnosis. Nidoni et al found conversion rate in males was significantly higher compared to females (p = 0.034, 95% confidence interval) [15]. Gold-Deutch R. et al also found higher conversion rates in males over females (21% vs 4.5%) [16]. But in present study, male sex was not a statistically significant predictor of difficult Laparoscopic cholecystectomy (p=0.571). It

is consistent with observations of Schrenk P et al and others [17,19].

16% patients (8/50) in present study had past history of hospitalization due to episodes of acute cholecystitis. In all these (100%) patients intraoperatively some difficulty was encountered. This factor was the most significant predictor of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy (p value-0.003). This finding is supported by Thyagarajan M et al. They found a conversion rate of as high as 34% in cases with history of previous attacks of acute cholecystitis. Liu et al and Khetan A also reported previous history of acute cholecystitis as a significant predictor of difficult LC [21,22]. Acute cholecystitis may lead to increased gall bladder wall thickness and cause scarring and fibrosis in and around gall bladder, making subsequent surgery difficult. This assumption is supported by the findings. In present study authors tried to correlate predictive factor with type of intraoperative difficulty. Previous history of acute cholecystitis caused significant difficulty in grasping of gall bladder, adhesiolysis as well as dissection of calot's triangle and dissection of gall bladder from liver bed (Table 2). Since intraoperative difficulty was encountered in all 8 patients with history of acute cholecystitis, understandably no relationship between intraoperative difficulty and number of attacks of acute cholecystitis was found. It is presumed that previous abdominal surgery; especially upper abdominal surgery may cause difficulty due to periumbilical and peri gallbladder adhesions. Nachnani et al reported that previous abdominal surgery poses problems during creation of pneumoperitoneum and during adhesiolysis to gain adequate exposure to the operative field [23]. But Kanaan et al and Lipman et al did not find prior abdominal surgery as a significant risk factor for conversion or prediction of difficult laparoscopic

cholecystectomy [24,25]. In present study also no statistically significant correlation ($p=1.000$) between history of previous abdominal surgery and intraoperative difficulty was found. Two (4%) patients had history of previous abdominal surgery (both had history of LSCS). Only in 1 of these patient difficulties was encountered during surgery. Since number of patients with previous abdominal surgery in present study was very small (only 2) and none of them had upper abdominal surgery, no definitive conclusion can be derived regarding this risk factor from present study.

In all 7 (100%) patients with duration of symptoms for more than 1 year, difficulty was encountered during surgery. It shows that duration of symptoms is an acceptable ($p=0.013$) factor for prediction of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy. This observation can be explained by the fact that patients with longer duration of symptoms are likely to have repeated attacks of inflammation leading to more adhesions and difficult surgery. In the series of 50 patients, 7 (14%) patients had adverse biochemical findings. In all 6 patients LFT was deranged. Leucocyte count and S. amylase/ lipase were normal in all patients. Out of these 6, five (66.6%) patients had difficult surgery. Murthy AK et al and Alphonat et al found that deranged LFT and elevated amylase is a factor for prediction of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy [26,4]. However present study found no significance ($p=0.181$) between deranged LFT and difficulty during surgery.

In the present series of 50 patients, 5 patients (10%) had thickened gall bladder wall ($>3\text{mm}$) on preoperative USG. Authors found no significance ($p=0.132$) between gallbladder wall thickness and overall difficulty during surgery, but in these patients' extraction of gall bladder was significantly difficult ($p = 0.006$). This contradictory observation could be due to

small number of patients with thickened GB wall. Larger number of such patients could have made overall difficulty significant. We did not find any significant ($p=1.000$) correlation between small/contracted gall bladder on preoperative ultrasonography and difficulty during surgery. In present study 1(50%) patients were reported to have small/contracted gall bladder on ultrasonography. Only in 1 of these patients there was difficulty in grasping of gall bladder, adhesions, difficult calot's triangle dissection and difficulty in duct clipping. Thickened gall bladder wall and small contracted gall bladder on preoperative ultrasonography is an indirect indicator of repeated attacks of inflammation and thus higher likelihood of fibrosis and scarring in and around gall bladder. Understandably it will result in difficult surgery. Agarwal PN et al found that contracted gall bladder and gall bladder wall thickness was a predictive factor for difficult LC [27]. But Carmody E et al did not find preoperative USG useful to predict difficult LC [28]. These contradictory observations regarding utility of USG are due to inherent limitations of technology besides dependence on quality of machinery and expertise of operator. In present study also actually only in one patient gall bladder was found small and contracted intraoperatively, the one with difficult surgery.

Lal et al stated that large calculus at neck region is associated with distention of gall bladder and multiple stones are associated with difficulty in gall bladder extraction through small incision of LC and hence may lead to perforation of gall bladder with spillage of bile and gall stones [27]. But in present study authors found no significance between single large/ multiple calculi and difficulty during surgery (p value - 0.088). Khandelwal et al also did not find calculus size or single calculus a significant predictor of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy [29]. Although 90% of

patients with adverse radiological predictor in present study had difficult surgery compared to only 30.9% of those with no adverse radiological predictor, this difference did not achieve statistical significance (p value - 0.066).

BMI more than 30 was associated with significant intraoperative difficulty (p value 0.049). It caused significant difficulty in gaining first access and extraction of gall bladder (Table 2). Obesity and abdominal fat is obvious cause for difficulty in the placement of the port, specially umbilical port and manoeuvring instruments through thick abdominal wall. Increased fat in calot's triangle also makes dissection difficult. Nachnani et al, Randhawa et al and others have found high BMI as significant independent predictor of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy [23,30].

Conclusion

Good clinical assessment is the most significant predictor of difficult laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Radiological predictors have inconsistent predictive value due to dependence on various factors beyond surgeon. So, it is important for surgeons working with infrastructural constraints to apply good clinical judgment and arrange specialized instruments, expertise, convert if necessary or refer to a specialized centre and counsel patients accordingly.

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